

Potential applications of nanotechnology in the management of environment and pollution control

Badal Kumar Mandal

Trace Elements Speciation Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail: badalmandal@vit.ac.in, badalkmandal@gmail.com Fax: 91-416-2243092

Manuscript received 21 December 2016, accepted 21 February 2017

The emerging field of nanoscience and nanotechnology with its potential and promise is leading to a technological revolution in the new millennium. Although there are many obstacles to overcome in implementing this technology for common usage, science is constantly refining, developing and making breakthroughs. Nanoparticles' performance efficiency is a function of their size, shape and surface morphology. A shift in focus has occurred from 'end-of-pipe' to prevention and process integration. Detecting and treating existing contaminants and preventing new pollution are among the challenges. In addition, new and better techniques for pollution control are emerging as nanoparticles push the limits and capabilities of technology.

Keywords: Nanoscience and nanotechnology, pollution control, environmental management, metal nanoparticles, metal oxide nanoparticles.

Introduction

In 1857 Dr. Michael Faraday informed that at the nanoscale properties of materials are size-dependent. After 101 years of his statement there was no report on nanomaterials in the literature. Although nanotechnology started its journey after the delivery of historic talk by Professor Richard P. Feynman titled "*There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom*" on December 29th 1959 at the annual meeting of the American Physical Society at the California Institute of Technology (Caltech), the scope of nanomaterials solely depends on how small it is, how smart it is and how scalable it is. There are lots of beneficial applications of nanomaterials in all fields around us. Despite a largely unproven track record in the environmental arena, nanotechnology offers great promise for delivering new and improved environmental technologies. *The Millennium Development Goals set by the United Nations are to supply basic services which nanotechnologies can find solutions for the millions of people in developing countries who lack access to basic services, such as safe water, reliable energy, health care, and education.* The scope of this chapter restricts us to potential applications of nanomaterials in the management of environment and pollution control. The authors like to highlight separately

on management of environment and pollution control with respect to uses of nanomaterials and hence nanotechnology.

Management of environment

Management of environment urges detection of contaminants in soil, water and air and afterwards monitoring them. Monitoring is an essential part of oversight. It provides the link between government actions and the real world. There are two areas of interest in environmental technology where nanocatalysts are potentially useful. These areas include (i) reduction of the pollutant emissions, (ii) decrease of the concentration of already existing pollutants. The use of engineered nanoparticles is rapidly increasing due to their applications in textiles, electronics, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and environmental remediation, which will release of such materials into the environment in long run. The basic structures of nanotechnology, which govern reactivity, include nanoparticles or nanocrystals, nanolayers, and nanotubes that could be used for pollutant sensing, prevention, and treatment.

A major cost of household expenses consists of consumption of electricity. Nanotechnology-based home lighting could reduce energy consumption by an estimated 10% in the

United States, saving \$100 billion annually and reducing carbon emissions by 200 million tons per year¹. Batteries are also being improved using nanoscale materials that allow them to deliver more power faster. Nano-materials that absorb enough light for conversion into electrical energy have also been used to recharge batteries.

Nano-heterojunctions, which integrate the advantages of nano-materials and heterojunctions, have attracted wide interests in many areas such as environmental pollution controlling area, because they can overcome two critical obstacles of TiO₂ photocatalyst: the dissatisfactory quantum efficiency and the neglectable utilization of visible light².

Nowadays, nanotechnology is a key focus of pharmaceutical industries for their promises in the advanced applicability and target selective approachability. A complete quality control protocol is urgently needed to assess the adverse effects of nanomaterials on human health and on environment after improper discharge. Again to properly assess the health hazards of engineered nanoparticles the whole life cycle of these particles needs to be evaluated, including their fabrication, storage and distribution, application and potential abuse, and disposal.

Nanofabrication of semipermeable membranes promises capabilities on the order of those of biological systems, and this in turn could provide much financial incentive for the development of molecular assemblers, as well established markets exist already³.

Particles in nanosize act as antibacterial, antifouling, and antidust catching nature. Nanotechnology is applied to purify water from *E. coli* bacteria and green algae by nano TiO₂ coated porcelain beads⁴. It also involves in increasing the oxygen content in atmosphere by decomposing water in the presence of nanowires of TiO₂ and UV light which is analogous to photosynthesis.

A Cu²⁺-dependent DNA ligation DNAzyme, a colorimetric sensor for Cu²⁺ has been developed using DNA-functionalized gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and can do on-site and realtime detection and quantification of the Cu²⁺ ion by using this sensor.

Cadmium and zinc containing quantum dots (QD) are more widely applied than all other quantum dots in the detection of heavy metals in aqueous solution. The analysis of

Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in water samples by L-cysteine, and thioglycerol capped CdS quantum dots⁵, copper ion (Cu^{II} and Cu^I) detection using an oligo (ethylene glycol) CdS quantum dot nanosensor⁶, and detection of Cu^{II} and Ag^I with a peptide-coated CdS quantum dot nanosensor⁷ were done. The quenching of the luminescence of quantum dots as a result of reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu^I by thioglycerol or an enhancement of luminescence i.e. two-fold increase in luminescence intensity in the presence of Zn²⁺ ion were the basis of quantification. The CdSe/ZnS quantum dots can quench luminescence with increase in cyanide concentration and estimate its concentration⁸.

A study also found emulsified nano iron particles can be injected into soil to treat groundwater contaminated by the dry cleaning solvent, tetrachloroethene (PCE) and its sister products. Some nanoparticles react with pollutants in soil to transform them into harmless compounds and also act as herbicides.

Air pollution monitoring

Air pollution is a serious problem in many heavily populated and industrialized areas all over the world. In addition to nitrogen oxides and sulfur oxides, many volatile organic compounds (VOCs) i.e. acetaldehyde, toluene, and hexane in air contribute to smog and high ozone levels and potentially damaging human health. Recently Japanese researchers from Toyota Central R&D Labs has developed gold nanoparticles in manganese oxide which are very efficient to break down VOCs at room temperature and has replaced most modern air-purification systems such as photocatalysts, activated charcoal or ozonolysis, because all these old systems are not able to break down organic pollutants at room temperature.

British nanotechnology specialist Oxonica developed cerium oxide based fuel additive as combustion improver which increased gas mileage by 5–10% and cut down nitrogen-based emissions. Although a tour bus company in Britain and another group in the Philippines have utilized successfully this additive, a leading oil company Petrol Ofisi from Turkey is ready to incorporate this technology. Nowadays Nanostellar is trying to replace pure platinum with platinum alloy reducing excess use of platinum and hence cost of the process with less diesel emissions without fuel additives. Also, many researchers are developing nanocomposites catalyst

which can replace very costly platinum for automotive catalytic converter. Altered electrical resistance of semiconducting single-walled Carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) through exposure to nitrogen dioxide or ammonia, forms the basis for SWNT molecular sensors. The nanotube based sensors also exhibits fast responses at room temperature to the gases and a substantially higher sensitivity than existing solid state sensors⁹. Although there is huge number of nanosensors available this chapter has no right to include them here. Light membranes composed of SWNTs can serve as efficient nanoscale vessels to encapsulate tetrafluoromethane at 300 K and a 1 bar external operating pressure¹⁰. Air conditioner industries can take advantages of nanomaterials for clean up harmful gases generated during operation. The nanomaterials with antibacterial activity are painted to inner surface of air conditioner, which can clean the harmful substances such as formaldehyde, xylene, or benzene from the outlet air as well as impart disinfection towards *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus*, *Candida albicans*, etc.¹¹. Nanophase Zn ferrites show very high efficiency for decomposition of greenhouse gas CO₂ to carbon and oxygen with little or no CO as a byproduct¹². Mesoporous silica SBA-15 with zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles (i.e. 3.04% zinc loading) shows the highest H₂S breakthrough capacity, 436 mg S/g adsorbent¹³. It is believed that ZnO-modified SBA-15 is a promising adsorbent for H₂S cleaning at ambient conditions, which would extend the application of the mesoporous materials to the environmental protection area.

The nanofilters having the pores of the size 3–20 nm can be used for controlling the pollution due to NO_x emission i.e. NO₂ and NO from the chimneys of the industries. Catalysts currently in use include a nanofiber catalyst made of manganese oxide that removes volatile organic compounds from industrial smokestacks¹⁴. Another approach uses nanostructured membranes that have pores small enough to separate methane or carbon dioxide from exhaust¹⁵.

Japanese researchers have found a way to collect the soot filtered out of diesel fuel emissions and has recycled it into manufacturing material for CNT¹⁶. The diesel soot is used to synthesize the single-walled CNT filter through laser vaporization so that essentially, the filtered waste becomes the filter. Carbon Nanotubes (CNT's) in quantity might become a systemic solution to the CO₂ emission from power-plants problem.

Although re-carbonization is encouraged all seem to prefer finding economical and safe ways to store CNTs rather than pursuing uneconomical processes to compress, liquefy and store CO₂ under the sea bed or in deep wells. Instead of platinum nanosteller Pt:Pd (2:1) NS Gold™ (Pt:Pd:Au) in light duty vehicles could be used for 25–30% better performance and thermally less corrosive to sulphur and phosphorus. Presently, CO₂ solution is commercializing its prototype reactor technology for coal-fired power generation, the oil sands and other CO₂-intensive industries where a low-cost capture solution is key to meeting climate change legislation in a cost effective manner. The NanoGLOWA project wants to turn this potential into reality to develop optimal nanostructured membranes and installations for CO₂ capture from power plants and removing benzene from petrol vapour at filling stations.

Water pollution monitoring

There are several nanoadsorbents such as nanoclays, metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, zeolites, nanoporous carbon fibers and polymeric nanomaterials available for water treatment and desalination technologies i.e. in separation technologies due to their high surface areas and extreme selectivity. The early impact of nanotechnology research has been mostly in remediation and end-of-pipe treatment technologies. A recent study from Switzerland has showed that in industry the mostly used metal NPs are TiO₂ > Fe oxides > SiO₂ > ZnO >> Ag¹⁷.

The distribution pattern of NP in consumer products is Ag >> Zn = SiO₂ = Ti > Au¹⁸. The most widely used NP in consumer products is TiO₂ such as photocatalysis, pigments and cosmetic additives due its versatile properties namely, self-cleaning, antifouling, antimicrobial and strong UV absorption¹⁷.

Water pollutants, such as waterborne bacteria, toxic metals, and chlorinated hydrocarbons, are introduced into the environment from natural sources and are produced from municipal, industrial, and agricultural processes. The remediation of contaminants in water, such as arsenic, chromium, phosphate, chloro-organics, and waterborne bacteria (e.g. *E. coli*), have been achieved by adsorption or dechlorination methods using iron and iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized from various methods.

Decreasing the pore size of the membrane to the na-

nometer range would increase the selectivity of the molecules allowed to pass through. Membranes that can even filter out viruses are now available¹⁹. Although majority cases ionexchange resins are used for water purification, ion exchange resins are easily damaged or contaminated by iron, organic matter, bacteria, and chlorine. The most common contaminant nitrate in drinking water causes two adverse health effects: induction of "blue-baby syndrome" (methemoglobinemia), especially in infants, and the potential formation of carcinogenic nitrosamines^{20,21}. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA) has set a maximum contaminant level (MCL) of 10 mg L^{-1} of nitrate-N in drinking water. The commonly used treatment methods for nitrate removal include chemical denitrification using zero-valent iron (Fe^0)^{22–24}, zero-valent magnesium (Mg^0)²⁵.

Oil spill is a critical environmental and ecological problem across the world. Nano-wires made of potassium manganese oxide can clean up oil and other organic pollutants 20-fold higher of its weight and could be reused due its extremely high heat-resistivity²⁶. The 2010 Deepwater Horizon oil spill in the Gulf of Mexico and Mumbai oil spill in Arabian Sea suggest that more efficient technologies are warrant to monitor and clean up oil spills in marine ecosystems. Nanotechnology can take the lead in near future.

Ceramic membranes, alumina and titania nanofibres, carbon nanotube membranes are promising in near future in separation technologies. Carbon nanotube-based filters are capable of removing various bulky hydrocarbons from petroleum during post-distillation of crude oil in a single-step filtering process and the filtration of bacterial contaminants such as *Escherichia coli* or the nanometre-sized poliovirus (25 nm) from water.

Other type of environmental treatment and remediation-related application of nanomaterials includes using dendritic nanoscale chelating agents for polymer-supported ultrafiltration (PSUF)²⁷. Nanoparticles such as the large band-gap semiconductors titanium dioxide (TiO_2) and zinc oxide (ZnO) being activated by light, used extensively to remove organic contaminants from various media. The technology also holds great promise for immobilizing heavy metals and radionuclides. Bimetallic nanoparticles, such as iron/palladium, iron/silver, or zinc/palladium can serve as potent reductants for polychlorobenzenes (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides, and halogenated organic solvents²⁸.

Majority research articles are available on the applications of zero valent iron nanoparticles (nZVI) for pollution prevention from aqueous solutions. Nano-iron particles can reduce almost all halogenated hydrocarbons (i.e. chlorinated methanes, chlorinated ethenes, polyhalogenated methanes, organochloride pesticides, heavy metals ions and inorganic ions) to benign compounds such as hydrocarbons, chloride, and water^{29–32}. Supported nanoscale zero-valent irons are used for removal of Cr^{VI} and Pb^{II} from aqueous solutions³⁵.

The successful uses of Fe-Pd nanoparticles are reported to dechlorinate chlorinated ethenes, chlorinated ethanes, trichloroethene (TCE), tetrachloroethene (PCE), dichloroethene (DCE), and vinyl chloride (VC)^{28,36,37}. There are many reports available on removal of both arsenite (As^{3+}) and arsenate (As^{5+}) by nZVI from aqueous solution^{38–41}. In the presence of competing anions such as SiO_2 , HCO^- , or PO_3^- , a greater amount of nanoscale zero-valent iron might be required to remove As due to reduction in As uptake. Compared to nonsupported nZVI, supported nZVI (Ferragels) was found more effective to remove Cr^{VI} and Pb^{II} from aqueous solution^{35,42}. Nanoscale Fe and Fe-Ni bimetallic nanoparticles were effective to remove inorganic selenate from aqueous solution completely. Removal efficiency of Fe-Ni nanoparticles is greater than that of nZVI^{43,44}. The degradation of monoazo dye Orange G in aqueous solutions has been carried out using Fe-Ni bimetallic nanoparticles⁴⁵. Nanoscale Fe and nanoscale Pd/Fe bimetallic particles has performed effectively for dechlorination of hexachlorobenzene in the environment⁴⁶. Ni-Fe nanoparticles for trichloroethylene to hydrocarbons⁴⁷, degradation of DDT⁴⁸ and 2,4-dichlorophenol⁴⁹ are satisfactory.

Montmorillonite-supported magnetite Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles (having 15 nm particle size) has showed a much better adsorption capacity of Cr^{VI} per unit mass of magnetite (15.3 mg/g) than unsupported magnetite (10.6 mg/g). In addition, supported particles are more thermally stable than their unsupported counterparts (having 25 nm particle size) and could be used for the removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution⁵⁰.

Other researchers^{51–53} have used Fe_2O_3 anomaterial for the remediation of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cr^{6+} from aqueous solution. Silica coated magnetite particles have been also used for the magnetic removal of Hg^{2+} from water. Silica coated Fe_3O_4 functionalized with c-mercaptopropyltrimethoxysilane has been used for extraction of Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} ,

Hg²⁺ and Pb²⁺ in a wide pH range and even in the presence of foreign ions acting as interferents such as Al³⁺, Fe³⁺ and Cl⁻⁵⁴. Fe₃O₄ particles encapsulated in thiol containing polymers have been reported to remove Ag⁺, Hg²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions⁵⁵. Porous MgO nanopowder (~38-44 nm in size) is capable of removing contaminants from aqueous solution and has removed 98% of reactive blue 19 azo and reactive red 198 anthraquinone dyes from aqueous solution⁵⁶.

Nano TiO₂ particles has been used for removal of 4-chlorophenol from aqueous solution. Uniform Au nanoparticles coated TiO₂ film can degrade photocatalytically bisphenol A which is a major component for manufacturing polycarbonate resins, epoxy and polyester-styrene resins from aqueous solution. Alumina nanoparticles have been utilized for the removal of heavy metals from drinking water⁵⁷. Both naked ZnO and activated carbon supported ZnO are highly efficient in mineralizing phenazopyridine and has removed completely within 50 min whereas ZnO/CdS system has showed lower efficiency⁵⁸.

Cobalt nanocrystals with highly ordered snowflake-like, cauliflower-like, ball-like morphologies can decompose thermally ammonium perchlorate⁵⁹. Polymetallic nanomaterials such as Cu_{1.25}Co_{3.75}/Al₂O₃, Cu_{2.5}Co_{2.5}/Al₂O₃, and Cu_{3.75}Co_{1.25}/Al₂O₃ are used to remove benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and first one has been found better than others⁶⁰.

Chitosan nanoparticles have been used for removal of Acid Green 27 (AG27), anionic eosin dye and nZVI for azo dye acid black 24 from aqueous solution. Instead of dyes it can remove as high as 3 mmol Cu /gram chitosan, 1–2 mmol Pt or Pd/gram chitosan, and up to 7–10 mmol Mo or V/gram chitosan^{61,62} from water.

Pollution control

Pollution control is control or prevention of harmful wastes. *Pollutants* are unwanted byproducts of manufacture or use. Manufacturing process control, compliance, ecosystem monitoring, and environmental decision making would be significantly improved if more sensitive and less costly techniques for contaminant detection are available. Regulatory bodies such as the United States Environmental Protection Agency and the Food and Drug Administration in the U.S. or the Health & Consumer Protection Directorate of the European Commission have started dealing with the potential risks posed by nanoparticles. Nanofabrication holds enormous potential

for effective pollution control, but high manufacturing cost prevents its mass commercialization.

Nanopollution is a generic name for all waste generated by nanodevices or during the manufacturing processes of nanomaterials. This kind of very dangerous nano-sized wastes being human-made causes living organisms' special adaptation to avoid adverse effects of nanowaste. On the other hand nanofiltration has a lot of benefit in separation technologies. Furthermore, nanotechnology could potentially have a great impact on clean energy production. Mega research is going on nonconventional energy sectors for more efficient solar cells, practical fuel cells, and environmentally friendly batteries using different smart nanomaterials.

Food adulteration

Milk adulterant melamine is known to cause renal and urinary problems in humans and animals when it reacts with cyanuric acid inside the body. The Kjeldahl and Dumas method used to test for protein levels fail to distinguish between nitrogen in melamine and naturally occurring in amino acids. Due to aggregation of nanoparticles the shift of the surface plasmon band to longer i.e. the color changes from red to purple (or blue) for gold nanoparticles and from yellow to red (or dark green) for silver nanoparticles, respectively^{63,64} might be helpful for monitoring adulterant in milk and milk products.

Melamine induced aggregation of Au NPs shows a color change from wine-red to purple, which provided a rapid and field-portable colorimetric detection of melamine. This method can detect melamine in liquid milk and infant formula with a detection limit of 1.0 and 4.2 ppm, respectively, within 30 min⁶⁵. It can detect as low as 0.15 ppm of melamine in liquid milk and 2.5 ppm of melamine in infant formula with UV-Vis spectroscopy.

The Au NPs in aqueous solution can be stabilized by coating it with negative-charged citrate ions. The amino group and ring nitrogen of hybrid aromatic strongly bind to the surface of Au NPs by the ligand exchange with citrate ions and decreases the electrostatic repulsion between individual Au NPs which finally leads to aggregation of Au NPs.

Removal of organic compounds

Highly crystalline ZnO and TiO₂ nanoparticles can degrade photocatalytically organic dye methyl red ((2-(4-dimethylamino-phenylazo)-benzoic acid)-C.I. 13020) under

UV and visible light illumination. The obtained results demonstrate a high photocatalytic efficiency of nanosized semi-conducting particles⁶⁶.

Evidence observed suggests that within the bimetallic complex, one metal (Fe, Zn) serves primarily as electron donor while the other as catalyst (Pd, Pt)²⁸. Surface-area-normalized reactivity constants are about 100 times higher than those of microscale iron particles. Production of chlorinated byproducts, frequently reported in studies with iron particles, is notably reduced due to the presence of catalyst.

Catalyst photocatalytic activity has been evaluated for the gas-phase decomposition of volatile organic pollutants (acetone, benzene, and toluene) under UV light illumination vs compound TiO₂ (Degussa P25). Results show the as-synthesized In(OH)₃ exhibited much higher photocatalytic activity and durability than In₂O₃ and TiO₂. This observation suggests that nano-sized In(OH)₃ has potential applications for environmental treatment, particularly for removing benzene-contaminated flue gas emissions from shoe-making facilities in China⁶⁷.

The optimised Pd:Ru (1:1) nanoparticle has showed the highest activity for hydrogenation of functionalised alkene under mild conditions. The catalyst is easily recycled under the reaction conditions without use of organic solvent which has reduced uses of organic solvent and minimized hazards in the environment. Trimetallic Pd-Bi-Au/C nanocatalysts have been found to be efficient catalyst in the oxidation of polyoxyethylene ether to corresponding carboxylic acid⁶⁸. Prati has demonstrated the ability of Au-Pd/C catalysts to oxidize diols, carbohydrates and aldehydes⁶⁹. Monometallic Co, Pd and bimetallic Co/Pd nanoparticles supported on MgO has dehydrogenated methanol to CO at room temperature catalytically. The Fe-Ni nanoparticle catalyst supported on Mg(Al)O has been used for the production of CO- and CO₂-free H₂ and carbon nanotubes (CNT) by nonoxidative dehydrogenation of methane. Similarly, mesoporous Co₃O₄ nanowires exhibit high catalytic activity in conversion process of CO to CO₂. This oxide bed could be used for conversion of toxic CO to nontoxic CO₂ gas.

Nanometer-sized zeolites (10–100 nm) have been used to selectively oxidize hydrocarbons, such as toluene to benzaldehyde⁷⁰ because visible light can initiate oxidation reaction by low energy pathways which help eliminate wasteful secondary photoreactions and increase the yield of the de-

sired product. In this study, selectivity for benzaldehyde using the nanostructures was 87%, compared to less than 35% for the same reaction with conventional zeolite material.

Ecological impact

A thorough ecological impact research is urgently needed to validate test methods; influence of de-agglomeration for environmental exposure; influence of physical environment of nanoparticles; and understanding exposure routes from environment back to humans. Implementation of control measures for the technology of environmental measurement, monitoring, and pollution control toward nanoparticles are needed. Several research reports have shown that biological treatment was entirely ineffective in removing the NPs. The addition of Al-coagulant removed only 9% silica NPs, but QDs was eliminated by sedimentation about 90%. Although alum addition and followed by sedimentation removed about 20–60% from a variety of metal oxide NPs such as TiO₂, Fe₂O₃, ZnO, NiO and silica, the lowest removal was observed for silica from aqueous solution^{71–73}.

Conclusion

However, we must remain mindful of the potential ramifications of this technology, including the fact that nanoscale materials can enter the food chain and be absorbed or transported by water and food. Bioavailability and toxicity of newly created nanoscale materials are largely unknown.

Nanotechnology is highly interdisciplinary and may present further challenges for environmental scientists and engineers to implement the technology of environmental measurement, monitoring and pollution control towards nanoparticles; to develop local environmental background exposure database for nanomaterials; to create nanotechnology knowledge bank on Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) of the concerned nanoparticles and finally to design synthetic technology for sustainable development using environmentally benign nanomaterials for all-round applications in food and crops, energy generation, drugs, information storage and communication, etc.

References

1. National Nanotechnology Initiative: The Initiative and Its Implementation Plan, NSTC/NSET report, March 2001, Washington DC; www.nano.gov/nsetrpts.htm.
2. H. Yu and X. Quan, *Huaxue Jinzhan*, 2009, **21**, 406.
3. S. L. Gillett, *Nanotechnology*, 1996, **7**, 177.

Mandal: Potential applications of nanotechnology in the management of environment and pollution control

4. T. K. Rao and Y. L. N. Murthy, *Nature, Environ. Pollut. Technol.*, 2007, **6**, 665.
5. Y. F. Chen and Z. Rosenzweig, *Anal. Chem.*, 2002, **74**, 5132.
6. K. Konishi and T. Hiratani, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 5191.
7. K. A. Gattas-Asfura and R. M. Leblanc, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, **21**, 2684.
8. W. J. Jin, M. T. Fernandez-Arguelles, J. M. Costa-Fernandez, R. Pereiro and A. Sanz-Medel, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, **7**, 883.
9. J. Kong, N. R. Franklin, C. Zhou, M. G. Chapline, S. Peng, K. Cho and H. Dai, *Science*, 2000, **287**, 622.
10. P. Kowalczyk and R. Holyst, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2008, **42**, 2931.
11. W. Cai, H. Li, Y. Zhang and S. Deng, *Huanjing Wuran Zhili Jishu Yu Shebei*, 2004, **5**, 58.
12. S. Komarneni, M. Tsuji, Y. Wada and Y. Tamaura, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 1997, **7**, 2339.
13. T. Sun, J. Yang, L. Zhao and J. Jia, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2008, **142**, 48.
14. Air Pollution and Nanotechnology. Available at <http://www.understandingnano.com/air.html> (18-12-2008).
15. J. Zhu and Z. Zhu, School of Engineering (19 September 2007). Available at <http://www.uq.edu.au/research/index.html?page=68941&pid=68941> (15-12-2008).
16. T. Uchida, O. Ohashi, H. Kawamoto, H. Yoshimura, K.-I. Kobayashi, M. Tanimura, N. Fujikawa, T. Nishimoto, K. Awata, M. Tachibana and K. Kojima, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, 2006, **45**, 8027.
17. K. Schmid and M. Riediker, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2008, **42**, 2253.
18. R. J. Aitken, M. Q. Chaudhry, A. B. A. Boxall and M. Hull, *Occup. Med.*, 2006, **56**, 300.
19. F. Tepper and L. Kaledin, Virus and protein separation using nano alumina fiber media. Available at <http://www.argonide.com/Paper%20PRE%20P%2007-final.pdf> (5-1-2009).
20. D. Majumdar and N. Gupta, *Ind. J. Environ. Hlth.*, 2000, **42**, 28.
21. C. H. Tate and K. F. Arnold, "Health and aesthetic aspects of water quality", in: 'Water Quality and Treatment', ed. F. W. Pontius, McGraw-Hill Inc., New York, 1990, pp. 63-156.
22. I. F. Cheng, R. Muftikian, Q. Fernando and N. Korte, *Chemosphere*, 1997, **35**, 2689.
23. Y. H. Huang and T. C. Zhang, *Water Res.*, 2004, **38**, 2631.
24. Y. M. Chen, C. W. Li and S. S. Chen, *Chemosphere*, 2005, **59**, 753.
25. M. Kumar and S. Chakraborty, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **B135**, 112.
26. J. Yuan, X. Liu, O. Akbulut, J. Hu, S. L. Suib, J. Kong and F. Stellacci, *Nature Nanotechnology*, 2008, **3**, 332.
27. M. S. Diallo, L. Balogh, A. Shafagati, J. H. Johnson (Jr.), W. A. Goddard III and D. A. Tomalia, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1999, **33**, 820.
28. W. X. Zhang, C. B. Wang and H. L. Lien, *Catal. Today*, 1998, **40**, 387.
29. C. B. Wang and W. X. Zhang, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1997, **31**, 2154.
30. W. X. Zhang, *J. Nanoparticle Res.*, 2003, **5**, 323.
31. L. Li, M. Fan, R. C. Brown, J. Van Leeuwen (Hans), J. Wang, W. Wang, Y. Song and P. Zhang, *Critical Reviews in Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **36**, 405.
32. K. S. Lin, N. B. Chang and T. D. Chuang, *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.*, 2008, **9**, 1.
33. B. K. Mandal, G. K. Gokul, K. Mohan Kumar, K. Siva Kumar, P. Sreedhara Reddy, B. Sreedhar and M. S. Hegde, *J. India Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 1477.
34. K. Mohan Kumar, B. K. Mandal, K. Siva Kumar, P. Sreedhara Reddy and B. Sreedhar, *Spectrochimica Acta (A): Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2013, **102**, 128.
35. S. M. Ponder, J. G. Darab and T. E. Mallouk, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2000, **34**, 2564.
36. H. L. Lien and W. X. Zhang, *Colloid Surf. (A)*, 2001, **191**, 97.
37. H. L. Lien and W. X. Zhang, *J. Environ. Eng.*, 2005, **131**, 4.
38. S. R. Kanel, B. Manning, L. Charlet and H. Choi, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2005, **39**, 1291.
39. S. Dixit and J. G. Hering, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2003, **37**, 4182.
40. K. Sasaki, H. Nakano, W. Wilopo, Y. Miura and T. Hirajima, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 2009, **347**, 8.
41. A. J. Feitz, S. H. Joo, J. Guan, Q. Sun, D. L. Sedlak and T. D. Waite, *Colloids and Surfaces. Coll. and Surfaces (A)*, 2005, **265**, 88.
42. S. M. Ponder, J. G. Darab, J. Bucher, D. Caulder, I. Craig, L. Davis, N. Edelstein, W. Lukens, H. Nitsche, L. F. Rao, D. K. Shuh and T. E. Mallouk, *Chem. Mater.*, 2001, **13**, 479.
43. K. Mondal, G. Jegadeesan and S. B. Lelvani, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2004, **43**, 4922.
44. S. J. Morrison, D. R. Metzler and B. P. Dwyer, *J. Contam. Hydrol.*, 2002, **56**, 99.
45. A. D. Bokare, R. C. Chikate, C. V. Rode and K. M. Paknikar, *Appl. Catalysis B: Environ.*, 2008, **79**, 270.
46. Y. H. Shih, Y. C. Chen, M. Y. Chen, Y. T. Tai and C. P. Tso, *Colloid. Surfaces A: Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 2009, **332**, 84.
47. B. Schrick, J. L. Blough, A. D. Jones and T. E. Mallouk, *Chem. Mater.*, 2002, **14**, 5140.
48. H. Tian, J. Li, Z. Mu, L. Li and Z. Hao, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2009, **66**, 84.
49. J. J. Wo, Z. Zhang and X. H. Xu, *J. Zhejiang Univ. Sci.*

- (A), 2009, **10**, 121.
50. P. Yuan, M. Fan, D. Yang, H. He, D. Liu, H. Yuan, J. Zhu and T. H. Chen, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **166**, 821.
51. L. C. A. Oliveira, R. V. R. A. Rios, J. D. Fabris, K. Sapag, V. K. Garg and R. M. Lago, *Appl. Clay Sci.*, 2003, **22**, 169.
52. J. Hu, I. M. C. Lo and G. Chen, *Water Sci. Technol.*, 2004, **50**, 139.
53. S. S. Banerjee and D. H. Chen, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2007, **147**, 792.
54. Z. G. Hu, J. Zhang, W. L. Chan and Y. S. Szeto, *Polymer*, 2006, **47**, 5838.
55. S. Shin and J. Jang, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, **41**, 4230.
56. M. Moussavi and M. Mahmoudi, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **168**, 806.
57. B. K. Hordern, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2004, **110**, 19.
58. H. S. Hilal, G. Y. M. Al-Nour, A. Zyoud, M. H. Helal and I. Saadeddin, *Solid State Sci.*, 2010, **12**, 578.
59. Z. T. Liu, X. Li, Z. W. Liu and J. Lu, *Powder Technology*, 2009, **189**, 514.
60. C. Y. Lu, H. H. Tseng, M. Y. Wey, L. Y. Liu, J. H. Kuo and K. H. Chuang, *Fuel*, 2009, **88**, 340.
61. E. Guibal, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2004, **38**, 43.
62. A. J. Varma, S. V. Deshpande and J. F. Kennedy, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2004, **55**, 77.
63. J. Liu and Y. Lu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 12298.
64. J. Lee, A. K. R. Lytton-Jean, S. J. Hurst and C. A. Mirkin, *Nano Lett.*, 2007, **7**, 2112.
65. L. Guo, J. Zhonga, J. Wu, F. F. Fu, G. Chen, X. Zheng and S. Lin, *Talanta*, 2010, **82**, 1654.
66. M. L. Curri, R. Comparelli, P. D. Cozzoli, G. Mascolo and A. Agostiano, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2003, **C23**, 285.
67. T. Yan, J. Long, X. Shi, D. Wang, Z. Li and X. Wang, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2010, **44**, 1380.
68. Y. Zhou, S. Wang, B. Ding and Z. Yang, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.*, 2008, **47**, 182.
69. L. Prati and F. Porta, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2005, **291**, 199.
70. A. G. Panov, R. G. Larson, N. I. Totah, S. C. Larsen and V. H. Grassian, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2000, **104**, 5706.
71. M. R. Chang, D. J. Lee and J. Y. Lai, *J. Environ. Manage.*, 2007, **85**, 1009.
72. Y. Zhang, Y. S. Chen, P. Westerhoff, K. Hristovski and J. C. Crittenden, *Water Res.*, 2008, **42**, 2204.
73. Y. Zhang, Y. S. Chen, P. Westerhoff and J. C. Crittenden, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2008, **42**, 321.